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Organization of the neurotransmission system in a human solid tumor.

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Total transcription was measured and compared in tumors from humans with glioblastoma, comparing the tumor core (center of the sphere shape of the tumor) and at the tumor edge (“rim”) to describe a basic 3-dimensional organization of a primitive neurotransmission system found in humans with breast cancer and in humans with lung cancer.

Results

The central neurotrophic factor, MANF, was enriched in the tumor core.

A second neuroactive molecule was observed to be enriched in the core region of the tumor in humans with glioblastoma, penkephalin (PENK).

Only one neuropeptide precursor was found to be enriched in the tumor core with MANF and PENK, a precursor for neuropeptide VF (NPVF).

We describe a basic organization for a prototypical neurotransmission system containing neuropeptide receptors of the NPY family, pannexin receptors and purinergic receptors, and neuronal pentraxin receptors.

In glioblastoma, the NPY1R receptor, neuropeptide NPY and NPY2R receptor were located in enriched quantity at the tumor rim. Purinergic receptors P2RY12 and P2RY14 were also enriched at the tumor rim. The neuronal pentraxin receptor NPTXR1 was found together with NPY1R, NPY2R, P2RY12 and P2RY14, and located in enriched quantity at the tumor rim.

Pannexin 1 was located (enriched) at the tumor core.

Other neuropeptides

NPBWR1 was enriched at the tumor edge, as was prepronocieptin (PNOC) and NPPC.

Hypothalamic pituitary adrenal (HPA) signaling

Adrenomedullin and angiotensin-like 1 were enriched at the tumor core. Pathway receptor RAMP1 was enriched at the tumor edge.

Renin was also enriched at the tumor core, as was the arginine vasopressin receptor AVPR2. The angiotensin conversion enzyme ACE2 was enriched at the tumor core as well.

Corticotropin release hormone CRH was enriched at the tumor edge.

Metabolic genes

KDSR, AHCY, HCAR3, SDHD, ODC1, ADSS, HK2, ACLY, CAD, PAH and FH were all enriched at the tumor core.

HAGH, GLUL and TAT were instead enriched at the tumor rim.

Tyrosine pathway molecule YWHAB was enriched at the tumor edge.

Other neurotrophic molecules or CNS-restricted genes

Neurotensin (NTN)
Neurotrophin 3 (NTF3)
Neuropilin 1
Myoneurin

LRRN4
LRRRC61
LRRRIQ3

Neurotransmission

The adenosine receptor Adora2A was enriched at the tumor core. Adenylate cyclase receptor ADCY1, ADCY5 and ADCY9 were enriched at the tumor edge. Adrenergic signaling receptors ADRB2, ADRA2C and ADRA1B were enriched together at the tumor rim.

Cholinergic receptor CHRM2 was enriched at the tumor core, while two other cholinergic receptors was enriched at the tumor edge, CHRNB2 and CHRNB4.

The majority of serotonin pathway receptors were enriched instead at the tumor edge, including HTR5A, HTR2A, and HTR1E.

Glutamate receptors GRIA1, GRIN2A, GRM1 and GRM5 were enriched at the tumor edge together with the serotonergic receptors.

Dopamine biosynthetic enzymes DCT and DDC were enriched at the tumor core. Dopamine receptor DRD4 was found to be enriched instead at the tumor edge.

GABAergic signaling receptor GABRA4, GABRA1, GABRAG2, GABBR2, and GABRA1 were all located together in highly enriched quantity at the tumor edge.

Guanine nucleotide signaling

GNL2 and GABP1 were enriched at the tumor core, together with RIC8A, a chaperone or GEF for G proteins.

GNAQ and GNAO1 were enriched at the tumor edge, together with the retinal G protein receptor RGR.

This component of the neurotransmission system also included of genes from the GNG and GNB gene families.

GNB1, GNB2 and GNB4 were together located at the tumor core, as were GNG5 and GNG12.

The potassium channel KCNE3 was enriched at the tumor core, while sodium channels SCN2A, SCN2B, SCN1B and SCN3A.

Visual system

Retinal genes RP2 and RP9, and the visual system homeobox RAX2 were enriched in expression at the tumor core.

Growth factors and growth signaling.

The growth factors HDGF and VEGF-A were enriched in expression at the tumor core.

GAS ligands GAS2L1 was located at the tumor edge while the ligand GAS2L3 was located at the tumor core.

Olfaction and taste receptors

Tas2R20 was enriched at the tumor core while a second taste receptor, Tas2R50 was enriched at the tumor rim.

1 Hormone and physiologic signaling

2 Gonadotropic hormones AMH and CGA were enriched at the tumor core.

3 Gonadotropic receptor GNHRH was enriched at the tumor rim. GNHR1 was instead enriched at the tumor
4 core.

5 ESR1 and progesterone pathway molecule PIBF1 were enriched at the tumor core.

6 Insulin degrading enzyme IDE was enriched at the tumor core.

7 Gastrin was enriched at the tumor edge.

8 **Discussion**

9 We described a basic organization for a prototypical neurotransmission system containing neuropeptide
10 receptors of the NPY family, pannexin receptors and purinergic receptors, and neuronal pentraxin
11 receptors.
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Methods

We measured total transcription using published or public microarray and/or RNA-sequencing data. GSE12689 was used for this study.